

Comparative Study of Seasonal Fluctuations in Physicochemical Characteristics of Aquaculture in Two stations of Tadikona village in Allavaram Mandal, Dr. B. R. Ambedkar Konaseema Dist. A.P, India

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ABSTRACT

Water quality plays a vital role in determining the productivity, sustainability and health of Aquaculture ponds. The present study investigates the seasonal variations of Physicochemical characteristics of Aquaponds of Two stations - T1 (Tadikona), and T2 (Tadikona- 2), over a period of one year (May – April). A wide range of Physicochemical parameters such as pH, Temperature, Turbidity, Alkalinity, Carbonates, Bicarbonates, Salinity, Total hardness, Calcium, Magnesium, Potassium, Dissolved oxygen (DO), Total dissolved solids (TDS), Nitrates, Nitrites and Ammonia were analyzed to evaluate water quality and its suitability for Aquaculture practices. The results revealed marked seasonal variations across parameters. Temperature peaked during summer (31.0 C - 32.0 C) and decreased in winter (28.0 C), while pH remained slightly Alkalinity (7.5 – 8.6), favorable for Aquaculture. Alkalinity and Bicarbonates were higher in summer, reflecting concentration due to evaporation, whereas Turbidity was higher during monsoon (up to 40 NTU) due to runoff and suspended solids. Total hardness, Calcium and Magnesium exhibited strong spatial variation, with extremely high values at station T1 (Tadikona-1) (5000 – 6000 mg/L), moderate at T2 (Tadikona-2), indicating site – specific ionic conditions. Salinity was increased range (5 – 13 ppt), showing minor seasonal fluctuations but slightly increased in summer. Dissolved oxygen ranged from 4.1 – 6.2 mg/L, with lower values during hot months due to higher oxygen demand. TDS mirrored hardness, being highest at T1 (Tadikona-1) and T2 (Tadikona-2). Nutrient concentrations were generally low, Nitrates and Nitrites were absent, while ammonia increased during summer, especially at T1 and T2 due to organic matter decomposition and feed residues. In aquaculture research, the analysis of seasonal variations in physicochemical water parameters requires statistical techniques. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was applied to determine whether significant differences existed among stations and across seasons. By applying ANOVA, the study was able to test the null hypothesis of no significant variation, providing a reliable basis for interpreting water quality dynamics and their impact on aquatic productivity.

Keywords: Aquaculture ponds, Seasonal variations, Physic chemical parameters, Water quality, prawns, Aquaculture. ANOVAs.

INTRODUCTION

Aquaculture is one of the fastest – growing food production sectors, contributing significantly to global food security, nutrition, and rural livelihoods. FAO reports (FAO, 2022). The success of aquaculture largely depends on the quality of water, which acts as

the fundamental medium supporting the growth, health and survival of cultured organisms. Water quality is governed by a complex interaction of physical, chemical and biological parameters, which directly influenced pond productivity and the sustainability of aquaculture practices. Pillay and Kutty. (2005).

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Among these Physico – chemical parameters such as pH , Temperature, Turbidity, Alkalinity , Hardness , Dissolved Oxygen (DO), Salinity and Nutrients (Nitrates, Nitrites and Ammonia) play a critical role in regulating metabolic activity, nutrient cycling and overall pond ecology. Sahu et al. (2007). Seasonal changes in temperature, rainfall and evaporation often cause fluctuations in these parameters, leading to significant variations in water quality across different months (Devaraj et al., 2013; Sharma et al., 2015); Natarajan et al., 2017). Such variations not only influence the growth of fish and shellfish but determine the carrying capacity and ecological balance of aquaculture pond. In the tropical regions such as India, where aquaculture ponds are exposed to distinct summer, monsoon and winter seasons, seasonal variations are more pronounced. During summer, higher temperatures and evaporation may increase salinity and hardness, while photosynthetic activity can increase pH and Dissolved oxygen. Conversely during the monsoon, runoff and rainfall reduces salinity, alter turbidity and introduce organic matter, which in turn may decrease oxygen concentrations. Winter months generally bring more stable conditions, through nutrient accumulation may affect pond productivity. APHA (1998) APHA (2012).

The present study focuses on seasonal variations of physicochemical parameters in a aquaculture ponds at station T1 (Tadikona) and Tadikona (T2) stations. Parameters including pH, Temperature , Turbidity, Alkalinity, Carbonate, Bicarbonate system, Salinity, Total hardness, Calcium, Magnesium, Potassium, Dissolved oxygen, Total Dissolved Solids TDS), Nitrates, Nitrites and Ammonia, (Boyd, C.E. 1998)[3] (Devaraj et al. 2013)[5] (Natarajan et al., 2017)[9], were systematically Analyzed (Rao et al. 2020)[11] across different months. These parameters were further subjected to comparative analysis between stations to assess site – specific differences and their implications for aquaculture management. (Devaraj et al. 2013, Jhingran 1991) The seasonal variability and comparative differences of water quality parameters (Das, S.K., et al 2018), is essential for identifying critical periods of water stress, potential risks of Eutrophication and the needs for corrective measures

such as aeration, water exchange and nutrient management (Sahu , P.K., et al. 2007), (Rout, S.K., et al. 2015) Such knowledge will contribute to the development of sustainable Aquaculture practices, improve pond management efficiency and enhance the productivity of cultured species. (Rout & Shinde, 2012). (Singh et al. (2018))

The study employed statistical tools, including mean, standard deviation, and analysis of variance (ANOVA), to interpret the significance of these variations. Statistical analysis is an essential component of aquaculture and environmental research because it allows researchers to objectively evaluate changes in water quality across time and space. In this context, Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) is one of the most widely applied statistical tools. It is used to determine whether the differences observed among groups, such as between sampling stations or across seasons, are truly significant variation. By comparing the variation between groups with the variation within groups, ANOVA provides a reliable basis for identifying meaningful patterns in water quality data. (Zar (2010) and Sokal & Rohlf (2012))

METHODOLOGY:

Study area:

The present study was conducted in the Aquaponds region, for a period of 2023 to 2024 at the Stations are T1 (Tadikona) , Latitude - 16° 31' 8.46" N and Longitude - 82° 1' 49.86" E, and T2 (Tadikona- 2) Latitude - 16° 31' 37.41" N and Longitude - 82° 2' 24.30" E. The samples were collected on the surface of area were located in Allavaram mandal in the Dr. B.R.Ambedkar konaseema District, Andhra Pradesh. India.

Water samples and their analysis:

Water samples are collected from the surface of the station were once in every month in polythene bottle at 10.00 AM from May 2023 to April 2024. All samplings represent instantaneous water quality at the particular time. Water samples were collected in polyethylene bottles, transported to the laboratory and analyzed. The analysis is carried out water samples are analyzed with respect to pH, Temperature,

Turbidity, Alkalinity, Carbonates, Bicarbonates, Salinity, Total hardness, Calcium, Magnesium, Potassium, Dissolved Oxygen (DO), Free CO₂, Total Dissolved solids (TDS), Nitrates, Nitrites and Ammonia. Water samples were analyzed for most water quality influencing 16 physicochemical parameters. which included pH, Temperature, Turbidity, Alkalinity, Carbonates, Bicarbonates, Salinity, Total hardness, Calcium, Magnesium, Potassium, Dissolved Oxygen (DO), Free CO₂, Total Dissolved solids, Nitrates, Nitrites and Ammonia. All the water samples were analyzed in the laboratory using standard methods. Data obtained from this study was statistically analyzed using the statistical package for social science (SPSS) version 16. Inter – station comparison was done using Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was performed to determine the point of significant difference.

Sampling Stations

The monthly observations of physico-chemical parameters at Stations T1 (Tadikona - 1) and T2 (Tadikona- 2), (May–April) showed clear seasonal variations influenced by summer, monsoon, and winter conditions. The results indicate that the water quality remains largely suitable for aquaculture, but with certain fluctuations that may affect pond ecology and cultured species. The overall mean values and standard deviations were also calculated to understand the fluctuations , Tadikona (T1) and Tadikona (T2)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

pH

pH is a measure of hydrogen ion concentration in water, pH directly influences the solubility and availability of nutrients and toxic substances in water. In the Two stations (T1 and T2), the pH values ranged from 7.52 to 8.60, indicating slightly alkaline conditions that are favorable for aquaculture. In the station T1(Tadikona-1) This station exhibited the widest variation, ranging from 7.61(May) to 8.60(August) can be attributed to intense photosynthetic activity and carbonate buffering during the summer months, which typically increases daytime pH levels. Station T2 (Tadikona-2) pH values remained relatively stable, with a mean of 7.96

and a narrower seasonal range compared to T1(Tadikona-1). This indicates a more consistent buffering system and reduced seasonal stress. Over all mean of stations ~7.93–7.97. Standard deviation (SD) ± 0.21 to ± 0.26 , reflecting low variability. The maximum 8.60 (T1- Tadikona-1) (August). The overall slightly Alkaline condition is optimal for aquaculture, as it promotes nutrient availability, microbial activity and fish growth. Station T1(Tadikona -1) is more prone to seasonal pH fluctuations, particularly during summer. Station T2 (Tadikona- 2) maintain relatively stable pH levels, which may reduce physiological stress on aquatic organisms. The analysis of pH across the two study stations (T1 and T2) revealed values ranging from 7.52 to 8.60, indicating a slightly alkaline environment throughout the study period. The study demonstrates that the pH dynamics of the ponds remain within the optimum. Aquaculture range 7.5-8.5 reflecting a balance between biological activity, carbonate equilibrium and seasonal environmental influences. Results from two way ANOVAs demonstrate that pH had in significant differences between stations and sites, null hypothesis accepted ($p>0.05$).

TEMPERATURE:

Temperature is one of the most critical Environmental parameters in aquaculture because it directly influences the metabolic activity, feeding efficiency, growth performance, immune repose, and dissolved oxygen dynamics of cultured species. Seasonal temperature variations were observed across the Two stations, ranging from 28⁰ C to 32⁰ C, which is well within the optimum range for warm – water aquaculture systems. In the seasonal variations of the three stations are summer (May – June) Temperatures peaked at 32⁰ C (T2, June), coinciding with higher Atmospheric temperatures and solar radiation. Monsoon (July – September) moderate values (~ 30⁰ C) were observed due to rainfall and partial cooling effects. Winter (December – January): the lowest temperatures of 28⁰ C were recorded across multiple stations (T1, T2) reflecting cooler climatic conditions. The mean value of Temperature is ~29.0⁰ C – 29.7⁰ C across the stations. The range of the temperature is 28⁰ C – 32⁰ C . In the standard deviation (SD) ± 0.97 to ± 1.26 , showing low variability. Among stations, T2 (

Tadikona- 2) recorded slightly higher variability (SD ± 1.26) suggesting that local pond conditions such as water depth, shading or circulation may have influenced temperature regulation. The values never exceeded stress Thresholds, confirming that the ponds provide a favorable and sustainable environment for fish and shrimp culture. Results from two way ANOVAs demonstrate that Temperature had in significant difference between stations and sites, null hypothesis accepted ($p > 0.05$).

TURBIDITY:

Turbidity is an important physicochemical parameter as it regulates light penetration, primary productivity and overall water quality in aquaculture ponds. In the seasonal variations of summer-Turbidity was generally lower ($\sim 28 - 32$ NTU), reflecting clearer water due to reduced runoff and sediment input. Monsoon (June – September) peaks were observed, particularly 40 NTU at T1(Tadikona-1) (June) and T2 (Tadikona- 2) (September – December), attributed to rainfall driven runoff, soil erosion, and suspended organic matter entering the ponds. Winter - moderate Turbidity values (30 -35 NTU) were recorded, representing a transitional phase where suspended matter settles gradually. In the stations T1(Tadikona-1), showed the highest Turbidity fluctuations (28 – 40NTU), reflecting greater organic load and suspended solids during rainy months. T2(Tadikona-2) displayed the widest seasonal variation, suggesting greater influence of catchment soil runoff and organic matter decomposition. In the Range of the 28 - 40NTU. The mean value of the Turbidity $\sim 32.5 - 33.5$ NTU. In the standard deviation (SD) ± 3.3 to ± 5.1 , indicating moderate variability. The higher SD values at T2 (Tadikona- 2) (up to 5.1). Moderate turbidity is beneficial, as it prevents excessive algal growth and stabilizes pond ecology. where anthropogenic activities and catchment inputs appear stronger. The mean values $\sim 32- 34$ NTU) fall within a range that supports productive aquaculture, but the seasonal peaks require monitoring and management to prevent adverse impacts on pond ecology. Results from two way ANOVAs demonstrate that Turbidity had in significant differences between seasons ($p < 0.05$) null hypothesis rejected and Turbidity had significant differences between sites ($p > 0.05$) null hypothesis accepted.

SALINITY:

Salinity plays a central role in aquaculture, as it influences osmoregulation, nutrient cycling, species distribution, and overall pond productivity. The observe Salinity values across the Two study Stations (T1,T2) revealed seasonal variations. The recorded Salinity values ranged between 5ppt and 13ppt, showing moderate fluctuations throughout the year. In the summer (March – June) T1(Tadikona - 1) showed the widest range (6 – 13ppt), indicating greater sensitivity to seasonal changes. T2 (Tadikona- 2) remained relatively stable (9 – 11ppt), suggesting natural buffering. T1(Tadikona-1) and T2 (Tadikona-2) maintained brackish levels (7 – 9ppt) but showed temporary reductions during peak rainfall months. Winter (October – February) moderate salinity levels were observed, with values stabilizing between 7 – 9ppt. This represents a transitional phase where monsoon dilution wanes, and evaporation begins to influence salinity again. In the station T1 (Tadikona-1) the mean value of salinity 10.46ppt and range of the station 6 – 13ppt are the displayed the widest seasonal fluctuations. High summer values (up to 13ppt) reflect intense evaporation and limited flushing, while monsoon dilution temporarily reduced salinity. In the station T2 (Tadikona-2) the mean value of the salinity is 9.92ppt, and range of the value 9 - 11ppt, it showed the most stable salinity regime, with minimal seasonal fluctuations. This stability is particularly advantageous for aquaculture, as sudden changes in salinity are more harmful than steady moderate levels. Results from two way ANOVAs demonstrate that Salinity had in significant difference between seasons ($p > 0.05$) null hypothesis accepted and Salinity had significant difference between sites ($p < 0.05$) null hypothesis rejected.

ALKALINITY:

Alkalinity is a crucial parameter in aquaculture systems because it determines the buffering capacity of water, preventing sudden changes in pH that can stress aquatic organisms. It mainly originates from carbonates, bicarbonates and hydroxide present in the soil and water and it directly supports processes such as photosynthesis, respiration and nutrient availability. In the mean value of the alkalinity ranged between 145 -159 mg/L across the three stations

suggesting that overall, ponds maintained moderately high buffering conditions suitable for aquaculture. In the standard deviation (SD) varied from ± 15.9 to ± 37.0 , with the highest variability recorded at T1(Tadikona-1), showing greater seasonal fluctuations. Seasonal variations of the alkalinity summer march – may) alkalinity peaked up to 244mg/L) at T1(Tadikona-1), likely due to evaporation concentrating dissolved salts and increased photosynthetic activity. Winter (November – January) moderate Alkalinity values were recorded , reflecting relatively stable conditions. Results from two way ANOVAs demonstrate that Alkalinity had in significant difference between stations and sites, null hypothesis accepted ($p>0.05$).

CARBONATES:

Carbonates (CO_3^{2-}) are present when the water pH is relatively high above 8.3. carbonates contribute to total alkalinity by neutralizing acids, helping maintain stable pH level in Aquaculture ponds. In the station T1(Tadikona-1) very limited carbonate enrichment was observed , with only a single peak in December (12mg/L).the absence of carbonates in all other monthly indicates that T1(Tadikona-1) is stable with minimal carbonate accumulation, possibly due to better water flushing or pond management. Station 2 -T2 (Tadikona- 2) displayed multiple enrichment events across seasons, with peaks in August (12 mg/L), September (8mg/L), December (8mg/L),February (12mg/L) and April (8mg/L). This can be linked to evaporation and higher metabolic activity , which concentrate dissolved salts and carbonates. T2 (Tadikona- 2) also responded with moderate values (August = 12mg/L , September =8 mg/L). post – monsoon / winter (October – February)- T1(Tadikona-1) recorded its only peak in December (12mg/L), while T2 (Tadikona- 2) also had enrichment in December (8 mg/L) and February (12mg/L). Station T1(Tadikona-1) - In the station T1(Tadikona-1) the mean value of the 1.33mg/L and standard deviation of the station is ± 3.55 . In the T1(Tadikona-1) showed the lowest mean carbonate concentration and relatively stable conditions. Station T2 (Tadikona- 2) - In the mean value of the station is 4.00mg/L and standard deviation is ± 5.12 . T2 (Tadikona- 2) displayed moderate mean levels and intermediate variability. multiple peaks in August ,

September, December, February and April contributed to fluctuations, reflecting recurring carbonate enrichment cycles. Results from two way ANOVAs demonstrate that Carbonates had in significant difference in stations and the sites, null hypothesis accepted ($p>0.05$).

BICARBONATES:

Alkalinity is a crucial parameters in aquaculture systems because it determines the buffering capacity of water, preventing sudden changes in pH that can stress aquatic organisms. In the seasonal variation of the summer (march –may) peaks in march (T1 = 244mg/L) indicate strong Bicarbonate accumulation due to evaporation and concentration effects. T1(Tadikona-1) and T2 (Tadikona- 2) maintained moderate levels (132- 156mg/L), reflecting dilution with rainfall but still retaining carbonate – bicarbonate buffering. Post – monsoon / winter (October – February) Bicarbonates generally increased, especially at T1(Tadikona-1) (February = 212mg/L) and T2 (Tadikona- 2) (January = 164 mg/L , February = 152mg/L). cooler conditions reduced decomposition, leading to gradual bicarbonate accumulation. In the station T1 the mean value is 152.33mg/L and standard deviation is ± 39.61 . T1(Tadikona-1) showed higher average bicarbonates, with considerable variability. In the station T2 (Tadikona- 2) the mean value is 156.33mg/L and standard deviation is the ± 28.26 . T2 (Tadikona- 2) had the highest mean bicarbonate levels among the two stations, but with relatively lower variability compared to T1(Tadikona-1). This indicates more stable bicarbonates contribution, possibly due to consistent soil water interactions. Bicarbonates concentrations varied between stations, with $T2 > T1$ in terms of mean values. Results from two way ANOVAs demonstrate that Bicarbonates had in significant difference between the stations and the sites, null hypothesis accepted ($p>0.05$) .

TOTAL HARDNESS

Total hardness is a measure of the concentration of divalent cations, primarily calcium (Ca^{2+}) and magnesium (Mg^{+}), in water . These ions play a vital role in aquatic systems, contributing to bone development, shell formation, enzyme activity, and overall Osmoregulation in aquatic organisms.

Hardness also regulates nutrient solubility, phytoplankton growth and the buffering of toxic and substances such as ammonia. In the seasonal variations of the summer (march – may April higher in T1(Tadikona-1) and stable in T2 (Tadikona- 2) concentrations increased due to evaporation and reduced dilution, leading to higher mineral concentration. Winter (Oct –Feb) - values were relatively stable, indicating equilibrium between input and evaporation. In station T1 (Tadikona) mean values is ~5,068 mg/L). standard deviation is the SD ± 841.28 mg/L. T1(Tadikona-1) has the highest mean hardness, reflecting a relatively stable and consistently higher mineral concentration compared to other stations. In the station T2 (Tadikona- 2) mean values is (~4,890 mg/L), standard deviation is the SD: ± 366.67 mg/L, T2 (Tadikona- 2) shows the most stable condition, with the lowest SD among two stations. This suggests that hardness levels here remain relatively steady throughout the year range 4380-5740mg/L), indicating less seasonal disturbance. Total hardness in the studied aquaculture ponds varied widely (1680 – 6180mg/L), with clear seasonal variations. Results from two way ANOVAs demonstrate that Total hardness had in significant differences between seasons ($p>0.05$) null hypothesis accepted and Total hardness had significant difference between sites ($p<0.05$) null hypothesis rejected.

CALCIUM :

Calcium (Ca^{2+}) and Magnesium (Mg^{2+}) are the principal cations contributing to Total hardness in aquaculture ponds. Both ions are vital for the physiological and structural functions of aquatic organisms, including shell formation in crustaceans, bone mineralization in fish, osmoregulation, and enzymatic activity. In the seasonal variations are pre-monsoon (march – may) calcium levels rise in most ponds due to evaporation and concentration of minerals. In the T1(Tadikona-1) (980-992 mg/L) and T2 (Tadikona- 2) (788 – 868mg/L).monsoon (June – September): fluctuations observed generally. T2 (Tadikona- 2) remains relatively higher except in august. Post monsoon / winter (October – February) - moderate and stable calcium concentrations in all ponds T1 (Tadikona-1) : 736-908mg/L, T2 (Tadikona- 2) : 744 -872mg/L), indicating

stabilization after rainfall and pond management practices. In the station T1(Tadikona-1) is the mean value is ~831mg/L and the standard deviation is ± 150 mg/L. is moderate variability. In the station T2 (Tadikona- 2) is the mean value is ~682 mg/L and the standard deviation is the ± 280 mg/L, high variability due to extreme low in march. Results from two way ANOVAs demonstrate that calcium had in significant difference between seasons ($p>0.05$) null hypothesis accepted and calcium had significant difference between sites ($p<0.05$) null hypothesis rejected.

MAGNESIUM:

The Magnesium levels in the Two aquaculture ponds (T1 and T2) were monitored monthly over a year. Magnesium is an essential mineral for aquatic organisms, contributing to enzymatic activities, Osmoregulation and skeletal development. The observed monthly variations indicate both seasonal influence and pond –specific characteristics. In seasonal variation of the pre- monsoon (March – May): magnesium levels were generally high in all ponds (T1 - 738 -906 mg/L: T2 - 680- 702mg/L) this is attributed to evaporation concentrating dissolved minerals in the ponds. Monsoon (June- September): levels decreased in and T1 (Tadikona - T1: 451-784 mg/L), showing the effect of rainfall dilution, while T2 (Tadikona- 2) remained moderately high (571- 673mg/L). post monsoon / winter (October – February): magnesium concentrations stabilize (T1: 588 – 694mg/L: T2: 578 – 709mg/L). post – monsoon / winter (October – February): Magnesium concentrations stabilized (T1: 588- 694 mg/L, T2 : 578- 709 mg/L), reflecting equilibrium in water quality after seasonal rainfall. In the T1 (Tadikona-1) station mean value is ~676mg/L. station T2 (Tadikona - 2) is the mean value is ~675mg/L. T1 (Tadikona-1) and T2 (Tadikona - 2) showed moderate variability (~147 mg/L and ~75 mg/L, respectively). T2 `s smaller function indicates more stable pond conditions. Results from two way ANOVAs demonstrate that Magnesium had in significant difference between in stations and sites, null hypothesis rejected ($p<0.05$).

POTASSIUM:

Potassium (K^+) is a key macronutrient in aquatic ecosystems, playing an important role in osmoregulation, enzyme activation and primary productivity. In aquaculture ponds, adequate Potassium ensures a balanced ionic environment for fish and crustaceans while also supporting plankton growth. In the mean values of the potassium 40-46mg/L across stations. Mean potassium levels were well within the range necessary to support aquatic productivity. In standard deviations of the 6.9 20.1 mg/L. The relatively high SD at T1 (Tadikona-1) (20.1) suggests that potassium concentrations fluctuated seasonally, with enrichment in dry months, while T2 (Tadikona- 2) displayed more stable profiles. Seasonal variations Summer (March – May) Potassium peaked at 65mg/L (T1, April). Likely caused by soil leaching and evaporation concentration, as well as Anthropogenic inputs (fertilizers, pond management practices). Monsoon (June – September) moderate levels 30-45mg/L due to rainfall dilution and runoff influence. Variability decreased reflecting more stable ionic composition. Winter (October – February) stable concentrations (40- 55mg/L). These levels supported consistent plankton growth and ionic stability, creating favorable conditions for aquaculture species. Potassium levels in the study ponds were generally adequate and beneficial for aquaculture, though T1(Tadikona-1) showed pronounced fluctuations driven by summer enrichment and monsoon dilution T2(Tadikona- 2), by contrast maintain more stable potassium levels, making them ecologically more balanced. Results from two way ANOVAs demonstrate that potassium had in significant difference between seasons ($p < 0.05$) null hypothesis rejected and potassium had significant differences between sites ($p > 0.05$) null hypothesis accepted

DISSOLVED OXYGEN (DO):

Dissolved oxygen (DO) is a vital water quality parameter for aquaculture. Adequate DO ensures proper metabolic functioning growth and survival of fish and prawns. Seasonal and site – specific fluctuations in DO can significantly impact pond productivity, health and species survival.. T1 (Station) - DO at T1 (Tadikona-1) showed greater variability, with dips as low as 4.3 mg/L during the monsoon season. This decrease is likely associated with higher

turbidity and increased organic decomposition, which consume oxygen through microbial activity. The low DO during monsoon is critical, as prolonged exposure below 5mg/L can stress fish, reduced growth and increase mortality risk. T2 (Station 2) - T2 (Tadikona- 2) exhibited moderate stability, with average DO levels around 5.5mg/L. This indicates adequate oxygen availability for aquaculture species and suggests moderate resilience to seasonal variations. Seasonal variations - pre- monsoon (March – May) - DO was moderately high (5.4 – 6.4mg/L), supporting active metabolism and growth of fish. Slight dip in T1(Tadikona-1) and T2 (Tadikona- 2) in May indicate potential stress due to warmer temperatures. Monsoon (June – September) - DO remained stable (4.8 – 6.1mg/L), benefiting from rainfall, water mixing and cooler temperatures. Post- monsoon / winter (October – February) - DO remained adequate (4.5 – 6.0 mg/L), indicating sufficient oxygen for normal aquatic activity. T1(Tadikona-1) as mean value is ~5.5 mg/L and T2 (Tadikona- 2) mean value is ~5.7 mg/L, the standard deviation of the other station T1 (Tadikona- 1) is $SD \pm 0.5mg/L$ and the other standard deviation is station T2 (Tadikona- 2) is $SD \pm 0.6mg/L$. The DO data indicate that all ponds maintain adequate oxygen levels through out the year, with natural seasonal fluctuations. Pre- monsoon and post monsoon months support higher metabolic activity in fish, while slight decreases during early summer and winter may require minor management interventions to maintain optimal pond health. Results from two way ANOVAs demonstrate that Dissolved oxygen had in significant difference between seasons ($p < 0.05$), null hypothesis rejected and Dissolved oxygen had no significant difference between sites ($p > 0.05$), null hypothesis accepted.

TOTAL DISSOLVED SOLIDS:

Total dissolved solids (TDS) represent the combined concentration of inorganic salts and small amounts of organic matter in water. TDS is key indicator of water quality and ionic composition, influencing osmotic balance, metabolism and growth of aquatic organisms. Excessively high TDS can cause osmotic stress, while very low levels may reduce essential mineral availability. Seasonal variations are the pre – monsoon (March – May) : moderate TDS levels T1

(Tadikona-1) : 532 – 646mg/L, T2 (Tadikona- 2) : 528- 642mg/L), showing gradual accumulation of dissolved minerals due to evaporation. Monsoon (June- September): TDS peaks in T2 (899mg/L, August), possibly due to pond isolation or localized mineral accumulation. Post – monsoon/ winter (October – February): TDS stabilizes T1(Tadikona-1): 501 -615mg/L , T2 (Tadikona- 2) : 501 -613 mg/L), indicating balanced mineral concentration suitable for aquaculture. In the mean value of the station T1(Tadikona-1) of mean value of ~587 mg/L and station T2 (Tadikona- 2) the mean value is ~620mg/L. The standard deviation of the station T1(Tadikona-1) is moderate SD ~75mg/L , and T2 (Tadikona- 2) station is standard deviation is high variability (SD ~140 mg/L) due to extreme value in august (899mg/L). Results from two way ANOVAs demonstrate that TDS had in significant differences between seasons ($p>0.05$) null hypothesis accepted and TDS had significant difference between sites ($p<0.05$) null hypothesis rejected

NITRATES:

Nitrates are essential nutrients in aquatic system, contributing to primary productivity by supporting algal and plant growth. Excessive nitrate levels can lead to Eutrophication causing algal blooms, oxygen depletion, and poor water quality. Monitoring nitrates helps maintain balanced nutrient conditions in aquaculture ponds. Seasonal variations are the pre-monsoon (march – may): slight increase in nitrate T1(Tadikona-1) : 0 – 0.18mg/L, T2 (Tadikona- 2) : 0 – 0.18mg/L) due to accumulation of nutrients from decomposition or pond fertilization. Monsoon (June - September) - Low nitrate levels (0 – 0.12 mg/L), reflecting dilution by rainfall and increased water turnover. Post – monsoon / winter (October – February) - nitrate remained low (0 -0.12 mg/L), indicating minimal accumulation and effective nutrient balance. In the mean value station T1(Tadikona-1) : ~0.06 mg/L and T2 (Tadikona- 2) : ~0.05 mg/L. seasonal variations are low overall (SD ± 0.05 – ± 0.06 mg/L), including stable nitrate levels throughout the year. Results from two way ANOVAs demonstrate that Nitrates had in significant differences between seasons ($p<0.05$) null hypothesis rejected and Nitrates had significant difference between sites ($p>0.05$) null hypothesis accepted.

AMMONIA:

Ammonia is a toxic nitrogenous compound produced from fish excretion, feed decomposition and microbial breakdown of organic matter. High ammonia concentrations can stress aquatic organisms, impair growth, reduce feed efficiency and in extreme cases, cause mortality. Therefore monitoring ammonia is essential for pond management and maintaining water quality. Seasonal variations are in pre – monsoon (March – May) ammonia concentrations were slightly increased in all ponds T1(Tadikona-1) : 0.4 mg/L, T2: (Tadikona- 2) : 0.55mg/L) due to evaporation concentrating nitrogen compounds and fish metabolic activity. Monsoon (June – September): Ammonia fluctuated at low levels (0 – 0.4mg/L), reflecting dilution from rainfall and water turnover. Post- monsoon/ winter (October – February) Ammonia levels were mostly negligible (0 – 0.5mg/L), suggesting effective natural conversion to nitrates through nitrification or pond management. In the station of the mean value of the T1(Tadikona-1) : 0.29mg/L and T2 (Tadikona- 2) : 0.40mg/L. In the standard deviation (SD) ± 0.03 – ± 0.21 mg/L. Ammonia concentrations in the ponds were generally within safe limits, with moderate seasonal fluctuations. while T2 (Tadikona-2) showed higher seasonal peaks due to organic matter decomposition and feed input regular monitoring and management practices, such as controlled feeding, proper aeration, and partial water exchange are recommended to prevent ammonia accumulation and ensure sustainable aquaculture productivity. Results from two way ANOVAs demonstrate that Ammonia had in significant difference between seasons ($p<0.05$) null hypothesis rejected and Ammonia had significant difference between sites ($p>0.05$) . null hypothesis accepted.

Table 1. physico chemical parameters of the seasonal variations in the stations Tadikona (T1)and Tadikona (T2)

Month	Stations	May	June	July	August	September	October	November	December	January	February	March	April	Mean	Standard deviation
pH	T1	7.61	7.92	7.81	8.6	7.96	7.56	7.98	8.21	7.84	7.89	7.89	7.96	7.93	0.269
	T2	7.58	7.88	7.98	8.19	8.12	7.68	7.95	8.14	7.89	8.21	7.87	8.18	7.97	0.203
Temperature	T1	29	31	28	31	29	31	29	30	29	29	30	31	29.7	1.05
	T2	28	32	30	29	30	30	30	28	28	30	28	30	29.4	1.24
Turbidity	T1	36	40	32	28	36	38	38	38	30	28	32	30	33.8	4.3
	T2	38	38	30	30	40	40	40	40	28	30	28	28	34.1	5.49
Alkalinity	T1	128	144	128	136	156	144	168	128	148	212	244	108	153.6	38.57
	T2	144	136	156	152	124	156	180	144	164	164	228	176	160.3	26.61
Carbonate	T1	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	12	0	0	0	0	1.3	3.55
	T2	0	0	0	12	8	0	0	8	0	12	0	8	4	5.11
Bicarbonate	T1	128	144	128	132	156	144	168	116	148	212	244	108	152.3	39.61
	T2	144	136	156	140	116	156	180	136	164	152	228	168	156.3	28.26
salinity	T1	11	12	11	6	10	10	9	10	10	11	11	13	10.3	1.72
	T2	10	10	10	9	9	10	9	10	9	10	11	10	9.75	0.62
Total hardness	T1	5410	5710	5550	2920	4670	4680	4450	4750	4980	5110	5710	6180	5010	841.2
	T2	4970	4980	4880	4380	4420	4780	4380	4810	4730	4970	5740	4860	4825	366.6
Calcium	T1	948	992	940	424	724	736	812	808	848	908	980	980	841.6	161.2
	T2	868	920	840	812	660	744	800	820	788	872	50	788	746.8	229.2
Magnesium	T1	738	784	777	451	694	690	588	663	694	690	792	906	705.5	113.2
	T2	680	651	675	571	673	709	578	670	670	677	811	702	672.5	61.18
Potassium	T1	0.4	55	45	35	50	50	45	50	55	50	55	65	46.2	6.89
	T2	0.5	45	35	45	45	55	50	55	45	45	50	55	43.7	14.8
DO	T1	4.3	5.1	5.6	5.9	5.7	4.5	5.6	5.1	5.8	5.6	5.7	5.8	5.3	0.5
	T2	4.1	4.9	5.8	6.1	5.9	4.9	5.4	5.3	6	5.9	5.9	6.1	5.5	0.6
TDS	T1	523	652	714	523	579	577	577	503	501	615	605	646	584.5	65.9
	T2	528	654	716	899	572	573	604	501	503	613	605	528	608	111.3
Nitrates	T1	0.1	0	0.1	0.12	0	0	0.02	0	0.02	0.02	0	0.18	0.04	0.06
	T2	0.16	0	0	0	0	0	0.12	0.02	0	0.04	0	0.18	0.04	0.06
Nitrites	T1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	T2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Ammonia	T1	0.4	0.2	0.25	0.4	0	0	0.2	0	0	0	0	0	0.12	0.16
	T2	0.55	0	0	0	0	0.15	0.5	0	0	0	0	0	0.1	0.2

CONCLUSION

The Analysis of physicochemical parameters in the aquaculture ponds at stations T1 (Tadikona-1) and T2 (Tadikona-2) revealed noticeable seasonal variations, reflecting the influence of climatic factors, hydrology, and pond management practices. These variations have direct implications for aquaculture productivity, water quality management and fish health. pH in water in all ponds remained slightly alkaline (7.5 – 8.6) favorable for fresh water aquaculture. Higher pH in summer (April -June) was likely due to enhanced phytoplankton photosynthesis, which consumes CO₂ and increased organic matter decomposition, highlighting the need for careful monitoring during low pH periods. Temperature, seasonal variations followed natural climatic patterns, with higher temperatures in summer (31 °C -32 °C) and lower in winter (28 °C– 29 °C) . Temperature influenced Dissolved oxygen levels and biological activity, with potential effects on fish metabolism and growth. Turbidity, higher Turbidity during monsoon (July – sep, up to 40NTU) was due to runoff and suspended particles, while clearer water in summer favored photosynthesis but increased the risk of algal blooms under high nutrient conditions. Alkalinity ranged from 96 – 244mg/L, with peaks in summer (March at T1 (Tadikona-1) : 244mg/L) due to evaporation concentrating salts. Bicarbonates dominated the buffering system, while Carbonates appeared occasionally in late Summer/ Monsoon. These levels indicate sufficient buffering capacity to stabilize pH , supporting fish health and pond stability. Salinity remained moderate (5 – 13ppt), with slight seasonal increases in summer due to evaporation and minor variation across stations. These levels are within tolerable limits for fresh water species, ensuring safe conditions for aquaculture. These levels are within tolerable limits for freshwater species, ensuring safe conditions for aquaculture. Total hardness varied significantly between stations, with very high values at T1(Tadikona-1) (5000 – 6000mg/L) compared to T2 (Tadikona- 2) (4380 – 5740mg/L). calcium and magnesium followed similar trends. Increased hardness is beneficial for shell formation in crustaceans and maintain ionic balance but excessively high values could limit fish growth, suggesting the need for periodic monitoring and possible water treatment. Potassium showed high

variability, particularly at T1(Tadikona-1) (0.4 – 65mg/L) and T2 (Tadikona- 2) (0.5 – 55mg/L). Dissolved oxygen (DO) ranged from 4.1 – 6.2 mg/L, with lower values in summer (May – June) due to high Temperature and increased oxygen demand and higher values in winter due to reduced decomposition and better aeration. Total dissolved solids (TDS), (358 – 899mg/L) same as Hardness trends, with higher values in summer and lower in monsoon, T1 (Tadikona-1) and T2 (Tadikona-2) consistently recorded . Nitrate and nitrite concentrations were very low, suggesting efficient Nutrient utilization or low organic load. Ammonia was mostly absent, higher values at T1(Tadikona-1) and T2 (Tadikona-2) during May – June (0.2 – 0.55mg/L), corresponding to periods of high feeding and organic matter decomposition. The two way Anova analysis indicated that certain physicochemical parameters exhibited in significant differences seasonal variations, while others remained relatively stable. The two – way ANOVA showed in significant differences across stations, while certain parameters varied seasonally. These results highlight the importance of monitoring water quality to ensure sustainable aquaculture management.

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